

**READINESS OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN POLOMOLOK
DISTRICT TOWARDS SCHOOL-BASED MANAGEMENT (SBM)
IMPLEMENTATION: AN ASSESSMENT**

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Readiness of Public Elementary Schools in Polomolok District Towards School-Based Management (SBM) Implementation: An Assessment

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the readiness of public elementary schools in Polomolok District towards school-based management (SBM) implementation and Assessment. The level of readiness of the selected public elementary schools in Polomolok District towards SBM implementation in terms of leadership and governance, curriculum and Instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and Management of Resources. The research method used in this study is a descriptive quantitative research design. The respondents of the study were the ten (10) School Heads, one (1)SBM Chairman, four (4)SBM Members, one (1)SPG, one (1) SGC officer, and two (2) PTA Officers of Lamcuah Elementary School, Landan Elementary School, Bato Elementary School, Maligo Elementary School, Palkan Elementary School, Lamcaliaf Elementary School, Kawit Elementary School, Guaza Elementary School, Bukay- Eel Elementary School, and Kawit Extension Tinifulan Elementary School. To determine the level of readiness of the public elementary schools in Polomolok District towards school-based management implementation and assess readiness, mean and standard deviation were applied based on the findings from the questionnaire survey given. As a result of the study's data, the schools' readiness in leadership and governance is evident through their strong leadership practices, precise accountability mechanisms, and collaborative decision-making processes. This foundation provides a solid framework for successful SBM implementation and fosters a positive student learning environment. The results show that in terms of curriculum and instruction, the schools demonstrate a high level of preparedness by prioritizing learner-centered approaches, involving the community in curriculum development, promoting continuous improvement, and nurturing values. The study also revealed a high readiness level regarding accountability and continuous improvement. Furthermore, the schools exhibit a high level of readiness in the management of resources. The result shows that the selected public elementary schools in Polomolok District are highly prepared for SBM implementation. It is recommended that this readiness of the schools for School-Based Management implementation will be sustained so that the schools will have better rating during the evaluation process.

Keywords: *educational management, level of readiness of public schools, SBM implementation, descriptive method*

Introduction

The Department of Education regularly implements programs and projects to upgrade the country's education system. One of the changes that Philippine education has faced was the implementation of School-Based Management (SBM) (DO NO. 83, s. 2012). A new paradigm in education called Revised School-Based Management (SBM) continuously seeks to increase effectiveness, quality, and equity. Its main goal was to develop a young generation that was capable and ready by using an active framework that promoted quality standard teaching and learning, adapting financial measures for a basic education continuity plan (DO NO. 19, s. 2020).

Ideally, this has been considered the governance framework of DepEd and is defined as a method for boosting academic standards by empowering individual schools to have significant control over essential decision-making. By providing them with responsibility for budget, staffing, and curriculum instruction choices. SBM gives administrators, teachers, students, and parents more authority to play a significant role in the educational process. This approach is believed to be an efficient way to improve community involvement, fiscal transparency, participatory decision-making, and accountability among school administrators. Despite the advantages of these systems from different sources, they have yet to be fully implemented throughout the country (Tacay, 2022; Tansiri & Bong, 2019).

School-based management (SBM) in the Philippines was modeled under the third Elementary Education Project (TEEP) was designed as a process project involving all stakeholders' planning, decentralization, consistent focus on schools and student outcomes, and information-based decision-making. Worth noting was the effective strategy of mainstreaming school-based management (SBM) as the integrative management framework of the project. It fostered social innovations, resulting in long-term governance reforms in the primary education sector, by fostering transparency, enhancing collaborative practices, and ensuring stakeholders' participation in almost all levels of decision-making. School-based management (SBM) cultivated the culture of innovation in DepEd schools (Maca, 2019). A national study's findings demonstrated that a particular element in successfully managing the educational system was the use of SBM by school leaders (Lubrica, 2019).

Several studies pointed out some constraints associated with school-based management implementation. These were lack of parental involvement, self-management issues, coordination issues, role overlap between the principal and school committee, lack of professional development for school leaders, and insufficient school funding are just a few of the challenges identified. Through school-based management and implementation, this stirrups community involvement to create a child-friendly, child-centered learning environment, and the principal plays a significant role in enforcing SBM (Kartika, 2020).

Locally, in Polomolok, South Cotabato, there were schools whose school base management (SBM) was still under the level 1 category known as the "Beginning" level. Despite its effectiveness in some contexts, there is still a need to prepare, work out, and analyze such programs. Thus, this study assessed the readiness of public elementary schools in the Polomolok District toward SBM implementation. This would help gauge the level of preparedness of the identified schools and be a basis for them to achieve SBM level 3 as a requirement to meet the quality standards established by stakeholders in providing learners with accessible and quality education (DO NO. 026, s. 2022). Hence, this study investigated the level of readiness of public elementary schools in the Polomolok District towards school-based management (SBM) implementation. This would help gauge the level of preparedness of the identified schools and provide the basis for them to achieve SBM level 3 or "mature" level.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to find out the level of readiness of public elementary schools in Polomolok District towards school-based management (SBM) implementation. Moreover, this study has the following objectives:

1. To determine the level of readiness of the selected public elementary schools in Polomolok District towards school-based management (SBM) implementation in terms of:
 - 1.1. leadership and governance;
 - 1.2. curriculum and instruction;
 - 1.3. accountability, continuous improvement; and
 - 1.4. management and resources?

Literature Review

This section provides a background and framework for the investigation. Selected literature related to the study was presented in this section. The review includes theories, principles, concepts, studies, and views related to the implementation and dimensions of school-based management.

School-Based Management

School-based management was considered the DepEd governance framework and is a strategy for improving academic standards by allowing individual schools significant power over crucial decision-making processes. In other words, under this, decision-making power is being decentralized to schools through RA 9155. With this strategy, school governance was strengthened, and parents' ability to reflect goals that benefit children's performance and learning outcomes was developed. This approach also permits collaborative decision-making amongst students, teachers, parents, communities, and school administrators (UNICEF, 2022). SBM practices were a component of enhancing the educational system. According to the study, it greatly aids in hitting the purpose, vision, objectives, and focus of the Department of Education, Philippines (Pepito & Acibar, 2019).

Moreover, school-based management (SBM) is a new paradigm in education that aims to improve efficiency, quality, and equity. Its fundamental purpose is to create a new generation that is ready and capable, using a dynamic framework that encourages teaching and learning. As a result, a school is a complex, interconnected system, not just merely a space for instructors and students. Further, this study showed the school stakeholders' enabling roles in the school-based management implementation are: Local Government Unit as assistance provider, alumni as organizers, students as helpers, parents as workers, teachers as facilitators, and school head as manager. The school stakeholders demonstrated and exercised civic involvement and an atmosphere of democratization in implementing the SBM process. Additionally, the Department of Education should give more substantial seminars and training with participation from school stakeholders for a more efficient implementation of SBM (Algonos, 2019).

In various world regions, school-based management (SBM) has functioned as a reform that has concreted decentralization in the primary education sector. The purpose of the study on the practice of school-based management on curriculum and learning in the Philippines was to examine the application of school-based management implementation to curriculum and instructional learning in the Philippines' public schools. It used a survey research approach on randomly chosen students and a purpose sample of English, Science, and Mathematics (ENSCIMA). The findings demonstrated that teachers used a variety of instructional strategies, notably in the three key subject areas addressed. Despite these practices, the study found that education is beneficial. Organizations must continue to work on initiatives and projects that will strengthen their community ties and links with other public and private institutions. This will aid in improving pedagogical strategies and instructional materials to react to the different demands of students to achieve a more effective and efficient curriculum and learning environment (Villanueva & Dela Cruz, 2019).

Furthermore, school-based management was centered on empowering, coordinating, and decentralizing the administration and managing school employees. Many nations have revised and adopted SBM to raise their educational standards. They view SBM as a fresh educational innovation that raises student achievement and school efficiency (Amon & Bustami, 2021). In addition, numerous studies provided evidence showing positive outcomes of SBM in different areas like academic achievement, school management, and student attendance, which has led to more countries implementing it (Isa et al., 2020).

School Leadership and Governance

School leadership or educational Leadership is the collaboration between the principal, teachers, students, and parents. This aims to raise the standard of instruction and the educational system by supporting our teachers in adequately educating our kids (Jensen, 2022). A strong school culture can be developed with the help of good Leadership in education. Its styles and strategies also affect how well students learn and perform through curriculum support, boosting learners' skills and abilities in administration and instruction. It is predicated on producing and harnessing knowledge in ways that have a helpful impact. The significant impact of educational Leadership is that it collaborates with different teams to develop partnerships and promote positive outcomes by creating and achieving transformation goals through cooperation and connections, diligence, and wise Leadership, even in critical moments to achieve goals (Cowan, 2019; Mamchii, 2023).

Furthermore, it should be noted that every social undertaking needs strong Leadership. Talented Leadership was essential to learners' success in schools. Leadership is frequently cited as crucial in explaining the difference between schools that do not support student learning and those that do. Students need guidance that will make them successful not only in the classroom but for life beyond graduation (Chen, 2020).

Education is a fundamental human right that works to raise children, men and women alike, out of poorness, with equality and ascertain process of improvement. One of the strategies advocated to reach the goal of the Education 2030 Agenda, which addresses the need to enhance the supply of trained teachers, is to strengthen school leadership to improve teaching and learning (UNESCO, 2021).

In these executive roles, position leaders search for ways to improve student education by engaging in different learning activities, allowing them to solve real-life situations. The principal is the prominent leader of the school, a capable leader who always sets a good example. He or she should be first to come and last to go out. He is always visible, alive, inspiring, involved in daily operations, receptive to suggestions, and observant of the school's and student's needs. Education managers can transform an average school into a flourishing school through proper leadership techniques (Chong et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the principal has new roles, responsibilities, abilities, and capacities under school-based management. In the framework of school-based management, he has the opportunity to govern a variety of leadership styles, including transformational, instructional, and visionary Leadership. Indeed, SBM was described as a period of change in school leaders' responsibilities and duties, especially during the new normal through the threat of the coronavirus that still haunts lives, which take part in school leadership initiatives. School leaders would reasonably support teachers, parents, and learners to be emotionally and mentally prepared. An exemplary leader always provides outstanding service for a significant educational change (Nidao & Ancho, 2020).

Curriculum and Instruction

Curriculum and Instruction were provided to all types of learners and should be localized to the best interest and benefits. All external and internal stakeholders work together to enhance materials to improve curriculum and instruction for varied learning experiences in teaching all learners regardless of their origin. In school-based management, one of the main principles is curriculum and learning, which focuses on addressing learners' educational needs and concerns and raising their academic performance. Through this, SBM was introduced as a way of life to make a difference in adjusting educational instructions and equip school employees to create classroom environments that support growth, innovation, contextualization, and ongoing professional development (Angeles, 2019). An international study conducted in Indonesia concluded that implementing SBM enables curriculum management and learning processes to be carried out effectively and efficiently, helps students develop positive traits, raises learning accomplishment levels, and enhances educational quality (Amon & Bustami, 2021).

Consequently, the prominent leader in a school building is the principal. A capable leader always sets a good example. A principal should be visible, upbeat, alive, inspiring, always involved in the school's daily operations, receptive to the opinions of his colleagues, and keen on the needs of students (Martin, 2019). With school-based management, curriculum, and learning processes can be carried out effectively, building students' wholesome attitudes, nurturing minds, and increasing the quality of education. Education leaders can govern and transform an average school into a thriving institution by boosting the efficient delivery of instructions.

Accountability and Continuous Improvement

Performance accountability is a management and oversight procedure that uses evaluation results and data from numerous other sources to administer the program, monitor performance, update stakeholders on progress, and enhance performance. It also entails actively monitoring processes and outcomes by correcting mediocre performance and praising exceptional effort. There was a sense of accountability, in which administrators and stakeholders were held responsible for the sources used in the teaching-learning outcome and their commitment to serve. The findings reported that increased parental involvement has resulted in the quality of school environments, which has resulted in considerable improvements in teaching-learning settings and student performance. The practice of SBM results is a substantial positive link between student accomplishment gains and better results in teaching-learning scenarios (Gwamanda, Vermaak & Bisschoff, 2019).

Resource Management

On the other hand, some schools distribute resources to achieve maximum efficiency. Resource management that constructing a fortified system entails planning so that the appropriate resources are allocated to the appropriate activities at the appropriate times. Setting budgets and making timetables for people, projects, tools, and supplies are all parts of managing resources. Resource management in the context of education is creating a strategic plan for allocating and utilizing school resources. Resource management implies assessing and maximizing available resources. One of the most decisive duties of school administrators was efficient resource management. When administrators evaluate their schools to determine what resources their students and instructors need, they start the process of effective resource management to provide the availability of the resources for effective results (Laranang, 2020).

Methodology

Research Design

The research method used in this study is a descriptive quantitative research design. A descriptive survey utilizes a variety of quantitative data collection and analysis methods, and the study design can apply a range of assumptions, from interpreted to critical theory and critical realism. The primary goal of using this research design is to see whether the dependent and independent variables are associated. It is non-experimental, whereby variables were measured using numerical terms. This design aims to gather more information on specific characteristics within a particular field of study (Creswell & Creswell 2018; Siedlecki 2020).

Participants

The public elementary schools that participated in the study were the ten (10) schools in the Polomolok District with School-Based Management under the Level 1 category. These schools are Lamcuah Elementary School, Landan Elementary School, Bato Elementary School, Maligo Elementary School, Palkan Elementary School, Lamcaliaf Elementary School, Kawit Elementary School, Guaza Elementary School, Bukay- Eel Elementary School, and Kawit Extension Tinifulan Elementary School. These schools were represented by ten (10) School Heads, one (1) SBM Chairman, four (4)SBM Members, one (1)SPG, one (1)SGC officer, and two (2) PTA Officers.

Instruments

The researcher gathered data through a self-made questionnaire adapted from the SBM Revised Tool designed as descriptive.

The questionnaire comprised the Revised SBM Assessment Tool items that assessed the level of readiness of the said elementary schools towards SBM implementation in terms of its four Principles, namely: School Leadership and Governance (five items), Curriculum and Instruction (seven items), Accountability and Continuous Improvement (five items), School Management and Resources (five items). All respondents should answer this part.

The questionnaire was constructed using information from numerous readings, works of literature, research by various authors, and sourcing from Deped orders and memorandums related to SBM implementation. The research adviser was provided with a draft of the research instrument for comments, suggestions, and recommendations. Three experts and one external validator verified the final draft before approval.

To ensure the questionnaire's utmost dependability and reliability, it was verified using Cronbach's Alpha based on standardized items. Before distribution and administration, the final revision was produced by including the experts' and various panels' corrections, remarks, and ideas. Experts will review and assess self-made questionnaires using the validity ratio to determine the validity of the research instrument. The research adviser will be given the first draft of the research instruments for criticisms, suggestions, and recommendations on how to present it more effectively while incorporating the adjustments. The researcher will submit the drafts for review by the expert panel. The validator has a thorough reading and does all necessary corrections to grammar, use of language and clerical errors, spacing, and everything necessary taken into account.

Reviewed and revised, the researcher created the final version of the questionnaire after taking the modifications, feedback, and ideas and returned it to the chairman of the examiner for the final critique. As a result, this study showed the readiness of the selected public elementary schools in Polomolok District towards School Base Management (SBM) implementation with an overall standard deviation of (0.54) with a significant mean of (3.99). It indicated that the level of readiness of the selected public elementary schools in Polomolok.

Procedure

Before the study, the researcher sent a letter to the validators and prepared the instrument for validation for three (3) graduate school validators and an external public school validator. After the survey questionnaire was validated, a certification was issued from the chairman and Vice President of Academic Affairs, and permission or notice to proceed with the study was obtained and signed by the dean of graduate school. To proceed with this study, the researcher obtained a letter of authorization that allowed the conduct of the study in the area, which had been evaluated by the adviser, signed, and approved by the Schools Division Office and the District Office. This letter was then sent to the heads of the schools where the data collection took place.

The researcher distributed the instrument to the respondents face-to-face while adhering to health and safety regulations. The researcher conducted an orientation to ensure the respondents' attentive response and manage the accurate data collected. After the orientation, the researcher provided them with the forms that needed to be filled out and responded promptly to any queries.

Statistical Tools

To determine the readiness of public elementary schools in Polomolok District towards School Base Implementation, the responses for every indicator in each principal were tallied.

Mean and Standard Deviation. These tools were used to assess the level of readiness of the public elementary schools in Polomolok District towards SBM implementation.

Results and Discussion

Level of readiness of the selected public elementary schools in Polomolok district towards SBM implementation in terms of Leadership and governance

Table 1 shows the level of readiness of the selected public elementary schools based on the data; the selected public elementary schools in the Polomolok district are highly prepared in terms of leadership and governance for school-based management (SBM) implementation. The overall mean score is 4.04, with a standard deviation of 0.55, indicating a high level of readiness.

The schools have demonstrated a high level of preparedness across various aspects of Leadership and governance. Firstly, in terms of having a development plan developed collaboratively by the school and community stakeholders, the schools exhibit a very high level of preparedness, with a mean score of 4.14 and a standard deviation of 0.56. This suggests that collaborative planning processes, such as the development of a School Improvement Plan (SIP) and Annual Improvement Plan (AIP) crafted by the a school planning team (SPT) involving school and community stakeholders is effectively implemented.

Furthermore, a network of Leadership and governance that guides the education system toward its shared vision, mission, and goals indicates a high level of preparedness. With a mean score of 4.08 and a standard deviation of 0.48, the schools demonstrate their commitment to ensuring that their educational objectives are responsive and relevant to the diverse environment in which they operate.

The schools also exhibit a high level of preparedness regarding organizational structure and work arrangements that promote shared Leadership and governance. With a mean score of 4.09 and a standard deviation of 0.59, it suggests that the schools have established clear structures that facilitate shared decision-making and define the roles and responsibilities of stakeholders.

While the mean score for the item related to a leadership network facilitating communication between school and community leaders for informed decision-making is slightly lower at 3.96, it still reflects a high level of preparedness. This indicates that the schools have mechanisms to enable effective communication and problem-solving for community-wide learning issues.

Lastly, a long-term program addressing school and community leaders' training and development needs signifies a commitment to continuous improvement. With a mean score of 3.93 and a standard deviation of 0.53, the schools demonstrate their dedication to enhancing leadership skills and promoting ongoing development. Overall, these results indicate that the selected public elementary schools in the Polomolok district have demonstrated high readiness for SBM implementation regarding Leadership and governance. The schools have shown collaborative solid planning, effective leadership networks, clear organizational structures, communication channels, and training programs. These findings reflect a solid foundation for successful SBM implementation in the district.

Table 1. *Level of Readiness of the selected Public Elementary Schools in Polomolok District towards SBM Implementation in terms of Leadership and governance*

<i>Items</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
In place is a development Plan (e.g., SIP) developed collaboratively by the school and community stakeholders.	0.56	4.14	Very Highly Prepared
A network of Leadership and governance guides the education system to achieve its shared vision, mission, and goals, making them responsive and relevant to the context of a diverse environment.	0.48	4.08	Highly Prepared
The school is organized by a clear structure and work arrangements that promote shared Leadership and governance and define the roles and responsibilities of the stakeholders.	0.59	4.09	Highly Prepared
. A leadership network facilitates communication between and among school and community leaders for informed decision-making and solving school community-wide learning problems.	0.62	3.96	Highly Prepared
A long-term program is in operation that addresses the training and development needs of school and community leaders.	0.53	3.93	Highly Prepared
Overall	0.55	4.04	Highly Prepared

Overall, these results imply that the selected public elementary schools in the Polomolok District have demonstrated high readiness for SBM implementation regarding Leadership and governance. The schools have shown collaborative solid planning, effective leadership networks, clear organizational structures, communication channels, and training programs. These findings reflect a solid foundation for successful SBM implementation in the district.

Level of Readiness of the selected Public Elementary Schools in Polomolok District towards SBM Implementation in terms of Curriculum & Instruction

Table 2 shows the level of readiness of the selected public elementary schools in the Polomolok district toward SBM implementation in terms of curriculum and instruction. The study results showed that the selected public elementary schools in Polomolok District are very highly prepared in curriculum and instruction for School-Based Management (SBM) implementation. The mean scores for all assessed items indicate a high level of readiness, ranging from 4.01 to 4.24, with a standard deviation of 0.63 to 0.81.

Regarding curriculum design, the schools demonstrate a very high level of preparedness. They provide for the needs of all types of learners in the school community, ensuring inclusivity and responsiveness (=4.24). The implemented curriculum is localized, making it more meaningful and applicable to the learners' lives in the community (= 4.16). Moreover, a representative group of school and community stakeholders actively developed methods and materials promoting creative thinking and problem-solving skills (= 4.17).

In addition, the schools also show a strong focus on monitoring and assessment. The community regularly and collaboratively monitors the learning systems using appropriate tools to ensure the holistic growth and development of learners and the community (= 4.01). Assessment tools for teaching and learning are continuously reviewed, improved, and contextualized to the learner and local situation, emphasizing the attainment of relevant life skills (= 4.17 and 4.02).

Table 2. *Level of Readiness of the selected Public Elementary Schools in Polomolok District towards SBM Implementation in terms of Curriculum & Instruction*

<i>Items</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
The curriculum provides for the needs of all types of learners in the school community.	0.68	4.24	Very Highly Prepared
The implemented curriculum is localized to make it more meaningful to the learners and applicable to life in the community.	0.65	4.16	Very Highly Prepared
A representative group of school and community stakeholders develops the methods and materials for developing creative thinking and problem-solving.	0.54	4.17	Very Highly Prepared
The community regularly and collaboratively monitors the learning systems using appropriate tools to ensure the holistic growth and development of the learners and the community.	0.81	4.01	Highly Prepared
Appropriate assessment tools for teaching and learning are continuously reviewed and improved, and assessment results are contextualized to the learner and local situation and the attainment of relevant life skills.	0.77	4.17	Very Highly Prepared
Appropriate assessment tools for teaching and learning are continuously reviewed and improved, and assessment results are contextualized to the learner and local situation and the attainment of relevant life skills.	0.81	4.02	Highly Prepared
Learning managers and facilitators (teachers, administrators, and community members) nurture values and environments that protect all children and demonstrate behaviors consistent with the organization's vision, mission, and goals.	0.77	4.12	Very Highly Prepared
Methods and resources are learner- and community-friendly, enjoyable, safe, inclusive, accessible, and aimed at developing self-directed learners. Learners are equipped with essential knowledge, skills, and values to assume responsibility and accountability for their learning.	0.63	4.13	Very Highly Prepared
Overall	0.68	4.24	Very Highly Prepared

Furthermore, the schools prioritized nurturing values and the creation of protective and safe environments for all children. Learning managers and facilitators, including teachers, administrators, parents, and community members, consistently demonstrate behaviors aligned with the organization's vision, mission, and goals (= 4.12). Methods and resources used in the schools are learner and community-friendly, promoting enjoyable, safe, inclusive, and accessible learning experiences aimed at developing self-directed learners (= 4.13).

Overall, it could be noted that the high level of readiness observed across all assessed aspects of curriculum and instruction indicates that the selected public elementary schools in Polomolok District have made significant progress in preparing for School Base Management implementation. Their emphasis on learner-centered approaches, community involvement, localized curriculum, continuous improvement, and the nurturing of values and culture bodes well for the effective implementation of School Base Management and the holistic development of learners in the district.

Level of Readiness of the selected Public Elementary Schools in Polomolok District towards SBM Implementation in terms of Accountability & Continuous Improvement

Based on the data in Table 3, the selected public elementary schools in Polomolok District are highly prepared regarding accountability and continuous improvement for implementing school-based management (SBM).

The mean scores for each item range from 3.73 to 4.11, indicating a high level of readiness across the board. Additionally, the standard deviations (SD) are relatively low, ranging from 0.38 to 0.65, suggesting that the responses are consistent and that there is a general agreement among the respondents.

The first item focuses on the roles and responsibilities of accountable individuals and collective bodies clearly defined and agreed upon

by community stakeholders. The schools are highly prepared, with a mean score of 3.85 and a standard deviation of 0.48.

Table 3. Level of Readiness of the Selected Public Elementary Schools in Polomolok District towards SBM Implementation in Accountability & Continuous Improvement

<i>Items</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Roles and responsibilities of accountable persons and collective bodies are clearly defined and agreed upon by community stakeholders.	0.48	3.85	Highly Prepared
Achievement of goals is recognized based on a collaboratively developed performance accountability system; gaps are addressed through appropriate action.	0.53	3.91	Highly Prepared
The community owns the accountability system, which is continuously enhanced to ensure that management structures and mechanisms are responsive to the community's emerging learning needs and demands.	0.65	3.73	Highly Prepared
. Accountability assessment criteria and tools, feedback mechanisms, information collection and validation techniques, and processes are inclusive, collaboratively developed, and agreed upon.	0.46	4.11	Very Highly Prepared
Participatory assessment of performance is done regularly with the community. Assessment results and lessons learned serve as the basis for feedback, technical assistance, recognition, and plan adjustment.	0.38	3.74	Highly Prepared
Overall	0.51	3.87	Highly Prepared

The second item emphasizes recognizing goal achievement based on a collaboratively developed performance accountability system. The mean score of 3.91 and the standard deviation of 0.53 indicate that the schools also have a high level of readiness in this area.

The third item highlights the ownership of the accountability system by the community and its continuous enhancement to address the emerging learning needs of the community. Although the mean score is slightly lower at 3.73, the standard deviation of 0.65 indicates that the schools are still highly prepared.

The fourth item pertains to the development and agreement upon inclusive criteria, tools, mechanisms, and processes for accountability assessment. With a mean score of 4.11 and a standard deviation of 0.46, the schools are deemed highly prepared, suggesting a solid collaborative effort in developing these systems.

The fifth item focuses on participatory performance assessment with the community, using assessment results and lessons learned for feedback, technical assistance, recognition, and plan adjustment. The mean score of 3.74 and a standard deviation of 0.38 indicate a high level of readiness in this aspect.

Overall, it could be implied that with an average mean score of 3.87 and a standard deviation of 0.51, the selected public elementary schools in Polomolok District are highly prepared for SBM implementation regarding Accountability and Continuous Improvement. This indicates that the schools have well-defined roles and responsibilities, a collaboratively developed performance accountability system, and inclusive assessment criteria and tools. The schools also engage in regular participatory assessments and use the results to make necessary plan adjustments and improvements.

Level of Readiness of the selected Public Elementary Schools in Polomolok District towards SBM Implementation in terms of Management of Resources

As shown in Table 4, the selected public elementary schools in Polomolok District show a high level of readiness in terms of Management of Resources for School-Based Management (SBM) implementation. The overall mean score is 3.94, with a standard deviation of 0.62, indicating a highly prepared level.

Analyzing the items assessed in the table, we can observe the following: Regular resource inventory is collaboratively undertaken by learning managers, learning facilitators, and community stakeholders as a basis for resource allocation and mobilization. The schools demonstrate a highly prepared level, with a mean score of 3.95 and a standard deviation of 0.54. This suggests that the schools engage in regular and collaborative assessments of available resources, allowing for effective allocation and mobilization to support educational initiatives.

In addition, a regular dialogue for planning and resource programming, accessible and inclusive, continuously engages stakeholders and supports the implementation of community education plans. The schools exhibit a highly prepared level in this area, with a mean score of 3.84 and a standard deviation of 0.53. This indicates that the schools prioritize ongoing communication and engagement with stakeholders to ensure inclusive planning and resource programming, aligning with the community's educational goals.

Resources are collectively and judiciously mobilized and managed with transparency, effectiveness, and efficiency. The schools demonstrate a highly prepared resource mobilization and management level, with a mean score of 3.85 and a standard deviation of 0.56. This suggests that the schools practice transparency, effectiveness, and efficiency in utilizing resources, ensuring they are utilized judiciously to meet educational needs.

Moreover, regular monitoring, evaluation, and reporting processes of resource management are collaboratively developed and implemented by the learning managers, facilitators, and community stakeholders. The schools exhibit a highly prepared level, with a

mean score of 4.00 and a standard deviation of 0.64. This indicates that the schools have established collaborative processes for monitoring, evaluating, and reporting on resource management, ensuring accountability and continuous improvement.

A system manages the network and linkages, strengthening and sustaining partnerships for improving resource management. The schools demonstrate a highly prepared level in this area, with a mean score of 4.05 and a standard deviation of 0.58. This suggests that the schools have established systems and processes to foster partnerships and collaborations, enhancing resource management practices through networks and linkages.

Table 4. *Level of Readiness of the selected Public Elementary Schools in Polomolok District towards SBM Implementation in terms of Management of Resources*

Items	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
1. Regular resource inventory is collaboratively undertaken by learning managers. Learning managers, learning facilitators, and community stakeholders as the basis for resource allocation and mobilization	0.54	3.95	Highly Prepared
2. A regular dialogue for planning and resource programming that is accessible and inclusive, continuously engages stakeholders and supports the implementation of community education plans.	0.53	3.84	Highly Prepared
3. Resources are collectively and judiciously mobilized and managed with transparency, effectiveness, and efficiency	0.56	3.85	Highly Prepared
4. Regular monitoring, evaluation, and reporting processes of resource management are collaboratively developed and implemented by the learning managers, facilitators, and community stakeholders.	0.64	4.00	Highly Prepared
5. A system manages the network and linkages, strengthening and sustaining partnerships to improve resource management.	0.58	4.05	Highly Prepared
Overall	0.62	3.94	Highly Prepared

As presented in Table 5, the data provides the level of readiness of the selected public elementary schools in Polomolok District toward school-based management (SBM) implementation. Overall, it could be implied that the findings indicate a high level of preparedness in all the domains of school-based management.

Table 5. *Summary of the Level of Readiness of the selected Public Elementary Schools in Polomolok District towards SBM Implementation*

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Leadership & Accountability	0.55	4.04	Highly Prepared
Curriculum & Instruction	0.68	4.24	Very Highly Prepared
Accountability & Continuous Improvement	0.51	3.87	Highly Prepared
Management & Resources	0.62	3.94	Highly Prepared
Overall	0.54	3.99	Highly Prepared

The schools exhibit a highly prepared level of Leadership and accountability, as indicated by a mean score of 4.04 and a standard deviation of 0.55. This suggests the schools have established strong leadership practices and a clear sense of accountability, providing a solid foundation for SBM implementation.

The schools also demonstrate a very highly prepared level in terms of curriculum and instruction, with a mean score of 4.24 and a standard deviation of 0.68. This signifies that the curriculum addresses the needs of diverse learners, is localized and meaningful to the community, and promotes creative thinking and problem-solving. Additionally, the continuous review and improvement of assessment tools further enhance the readiness level in this area.

The schools show a highly prepared level regarding accountability and continuous improvement, with a mean score of 3.87 and a standard deviation of 0.51. This indicates that the schools have clearly defined roles and responsibilities, recognize goal achievement through a performance accountability system, and engage in participatory assessment and feedback processes. However, there is room for further enhancement regarding community ownership of the accountability system.

Regarding management and resources, the schools exhibit a highly prepared level, with a mean score of 3.94 and a standard deviation of 0.62. This suggests that the schools engage in regular resource inventory, collaborative planning, judicious mobilization and management of resources, and effective monitoring and reporting processes. The presence of systems to manage networks and linkages strengthens partnerships for resource improvement.

Furthermore, the selected public elementary schools in Polomolok District display high readiness for SBM implementation. With highly prepared levels observed across Leadership and accountability, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and management and resources, the schools possess the necessary foundations to implement SBM successfully. These findings indicate a positive outlook for the district regarding achieving educational goals and improving overall school performance. It could be further implied that the schools are very highly ready in the implementation of school-based management especially in terms of curriculum and instruction domain.

Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, the following conclusions are drawn: The schools are highly prepared for the implementation of School-

Based Management in terms of leadership and accountability. On the other hand, they are very highly prepared in terms of curriculum and instruction domain. Additionally, the schools are highly prepared in terms of Accountability & Continuous Improvement. Lastly, they are highly prepared in terms of Management & Resources

The result shows that the selected public elementary schools in Polomolok District are highly prepared for SBM implementation. The readiness in leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and management of resources sets a strong foundation for a successful SBM Implementation that promotes quality education in the district that radiates its practices to be benchmarked by other schools and districts.

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